

Beyond Two Dimensions: Large-Scale Building Height Mapping in OpenStreetMap via Synthetic Aperture Radar and Street-View Imagery

Hao Li^{1,*} and Yao Sun²

¹ Professorship of Big Geospatial Data Management, Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany; hao_bgd.li@tum.de

² Chair in Data Science in Earth Observation, Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany; yao.sun@tum.de

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

This abstract was accepted to the OSM Science 2023 Conference after peer-review.

In the past decades, the world has been comprehensively mapped in 2D, however, a vertical dimension remains underexplored despite its huge potential. For instance, as of August 2023, more than 571 million buildings are mapped in OpenStreetMap (OSM) according to statistics from Taginfo, but less than 3% of them are associated with height values via the key/value pairs *heights=**. Though one can often estimate the height information via OSM key/value pairs such as *building:levels=** and *stories=**. Mapping human settlements as a 3D representation of reality requires an accurate description of vertical dimensions besides the 2D footprints and shapes. A 3D representation of human settlement is important in many aspects, including public health, urban planning, and environment monitoring, disaster management, etc. In this context, a list of the most relevant 3D building attributes mainly includes but is not limited to building height, building floor, and roof type [1,2]. For instance, building height is a key and fundamental factor in post-disaster (e.g., earthquake and flood) damage and situation assessment. Similarly, the roof type information is beneficial in estimating photovoltaic electricity potential at scale. As defined in CityGML 2.0 [3], 3D building models are divided into five levels of detail (LoDs) [4]. In LoD0, only the 2D footprint information is involved in the model. In LoD1, the LoD0 model is extruded by their building heights, and the obtained cuboid after extrusion is the LoD1 model. In LoD2, the 3D roof structure information is added to the LoD2 model. The LoD3 model further contains facade elements such as windows and doors. The LoD4 model is more complicated and contains both external and internal building elements. However, there are still open questions about how to automatically generate large-scale and fine-grained 3D building attributes in a fully reproducible and generalizable manner. Moreover, how to integrate such information into OSM or existing mapping tools.

Li, H., & Sun, Y. (2023). Beyond Two Dimensions: Large-Scale Building Height Mapping in OpenStreetMap via Synthetic Aperture Radar and Street-View Imagery

In: Minghini, M., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., Liu, P., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., Coetzee, S., Mooney, P., Sarretta, A., & Anderson, J. (Eds.). Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023, Antwerp, Belgium, 10-12 November 2023. Available at

<https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2023>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10443329](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443329)

© 2023 by the authors. Available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)) license.

Traditional studies on building height retrieval in the Remote Sensing (RS) domain primarily employ high-resolution optical images and airborne LiDAR data [5]. However, optical data acquisition requires cloud-free weather, and airborne or terrestrial data are too expensive to collect globally. This proposal reports recent advances in supplementing OSM data with large-scale building height, specifically using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data and Street-View Images (SVI) data.

SAR data have been employed for modeling buildings due to their imaging capability regardless of the time or weather conditions. Since the launch of TerraSAR-X in 2007, modern SAR satellites, e.g., TerraSAR-X, TanDEM-X, and CosmoSky-Med, have been providing meter or even sub-meter resolution images, making it possible to extract and reconstruct man-made objects from spaceborne SAR data. Complete global coverages of TerraSAR-X/TanDEM-X stripmap mode data have been acquired since 2012, offering significant potential as a data source for worldwide building reconstruction [6]. Nonetheless, owing to the side-looking geometry and employment of one-band radar sensors, urban structures appear distinct in SAR images but pose challenges in differentiation. Researchers have investigated building height retrieval from a single SAR image, InSAR data, and multi-aspect SAR or InSAR data or even circular SAR to overcome the limitations resulting from the side-looking geometry, especially occlusions [7-9].

While building reconstruction with SAR data has been extensively researched, large-scale studies are limited. Deep neural networks, gaining prominence for breakthroughs across various domains including remote sensing, face a key hurdle in urban SAR analysis: the scarcity of annotated data. To address this issue, the authors annotated individual buildings in a TerraSAR-X spotlight image employing a highly accurate Digital Surface Model (DSM) and proposed a segmentation network for predicting building areas in the SAR image [10]. The segmentation results are then applied to reconstruct building heights. The extracted building segments are then employed for LoD1 model reconstruction and achieved the mean height error of 2.39 m in the study site of Berlin. To reconstruct buildings in larger areas, more training data are needed. However, accurate DSMs are unavailable in most cases. Therefore, the LoD1 building reconstruction problem is reformulated as a bounding box regression problem in [11] so that height data from multiple sources can be employed to generate bounding boxes of buildings. A regression network is proposed and examined for four study sites using TerraSAR-X spotlight and stripmap mode images. The absolute mean height error achieved in the four sites ranges from 4.3m to 5.7m, which is significant, given that they are achieved from a single stripmap/spotlight TerraSAR-X image.

Compared with photogrammetry and RS data, SVI data and 2D building footprint data are easier and cheaper to be collected and processed (e.g., Mapillary and OSM). There have been some early efforts to estimate building height based on these new data sources. More specifically, one can extract multi-level morphological features (or urban-form features) in predicting key attributes (e.g., height, function, energy consumption, etc.) of buildings and streets from an urban analytic perspective, then use these features with a machine learning (ML) model for supervised or semi-supervised building height regression.

In [12], a novel semi-supervised method was developed for building floor estimation based on automatic facade parsing and urban architecture rules. In short, the authors seek to generate the estimation of building floor or height (by multiplying an average floor height) as the "pseudo label" to guide ML regression models with OSM morphometric features [2] as covariates. The developed method consists of three main steps: 1) SVI and OSM building

alignment: we used the compass angle and geotagged coordinates of the camera of SVI and applied a ray-tracing method to determine their relationship. 2) Facade object detection: we use a pre-trained one-stage object detection network (YOLO v3) to detect key facade features (e.g., window, balcony, and door) [13]. 3) Building floor estimation: based on facade object detection results, one can then apply a rule-based approach to determine the floor number in order to estimate the height of corresponding OSM buildings, which is used as "pseudo labels" to train an ML-based building height estimation model. As a case study, the authors validate the proposed method in the city of Heidelberg, Germany, and the preliminary result looks very promising with a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of around 2.1 meters for 308 OSM buildings.

As lessons learned, the potential of SVI in mapping large-scale 3D building attributes are acknowledged, while it still has its own limitation regarding data quality and estimation accuracy. Therefore, a potential solution is to conduct data and model fusion of RS data, especially with SAR imagery, and crowdsourcing data (e.g., OSM and SVI) in large-scale real-world mapping and data-producing scenarios. One can imagine a conceptual framework, which can include multiple data sources and data views (street-level and overhead) and explore their synergies w.r.t granularity, scalability, availability, and computational efficiency for automatic 3D building attribute mapping, which shall then benefit the OSM community by enriching the OSM building attribute data quality in a longer term [14,15].

To sum up, we share the latest developments in large-scale 3D building attribute mapping in OpenStreetMap with two solid case studies using SAR and SVI, which sheds important light on the future research direction in this emerging research area. We expect this research stream will make a long-term and sustainable impact in numerous downstream applications within urban planning, disaster response, and global environmental monitoring and mapping.

References

- [1] Biljecki, F., & Chow, Y. S. (2022). Global building morphology indicators. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 95, 101809.
- [2] Milojevic-Dupont, N., Hans, N., Kaack, L. H., Zumwald, M., Andrieux, F., de Barros Soares, D., Lohrey, S., Pichler, P.-P., & Creutzig, F. (2020). Learning from urban form to predict building heights. *PLOS one*, 15(12), e0242010.
- [3] Kolbe, T. H., Gröger, G., & Plümer, L. (2008). CityGML–3D city models and their potential for emergency response. In S. Zlatanova, & J. Li (Eds.), *Geospatial information technology for emergency response* (pp. 257–274). Taylor & Francis.
- [4] Fan, H., & Meng, L. (2012). A three-step approach of simplifying 3D buildings modeled by CityGML. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 26(6), 1091–1107.
- [5] Alobeid, A., Jacobsen, K., & Heipke, C. (2009). Building height estimation in urban areas from very high resolution satellite stereo images. In *ISPRS Hannover Workshop* (pp. 2–5).
- [6] Zhu, X. X., Sun, Y., Shi, Y., Wang, Y., & Ge, N. (2018). Towards global 3d/4d urban modeling using tandem-x data. In *EUSAR 2018; 12th European Conference on Synthetic Aperture Radar* (pp. 1-6). VDE.
- [7] Soergel, U., Michaelsen, E., Thiele, A., Cadario, E., & Thoennessen, U. (2009). Stereo analysis of high-resolution SAR images for building height estimation in cases of orthogonal aspect directions. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 64(5), 490–500.
- [8] Dubois, C., Thiele, A., & Hinz, S. (2016). Building detection and building parameter retrieval in InSAR phase images. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 114, 228–241.

- [9] Xu, F., Jin, Y.-Q. (2007). Automatic reconstruction of building objects from multiaspect meter-resolution SAR images. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 45(7), 2336–2353.
- [10] Sun, Y., Hua, Y., Mou, L., & Zhu, X. X. (2021). CG-Net: Conditional GIS-Aware network for individual building segmentation in VHR SAR images. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, 1-15.
- [11] Sun, Y., Mou, L., Wang, Y., Montazeri, S., & Zhu, X. X. (2022). Large-scale building height retrieval from single SAR imagery based on bounding box regression networks. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 184, 79-95.
- [12] Li, H., Yuan, Z., Dax, G., Kong, G., Fan, H., Zipf, A., & Werner, M. (2023). Semi-Supervised Learning from Street-View Images and OpenStreetMap for Automatic Building Height Estimation. In *12th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2023)*. Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik.
- [13] Kong, G., & Fan, H. (2020). Enhanced facade parsing for street-level images using convolutional neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 59(12), 10519-10531.
- [14] Sun, Y., Kruspe, A., Meng, L., Tian, Y., Hoffmann, E. J., Auer, S., & Zhu, X. X. (2023). *Towards Large-scale Building Attribute Mapping using Crowdsourced Images: Scene Text Recognition on Flickr and Problems to be Solved*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.08042>
- [15] Herfort, B., Lautenbach, S., Porto de Albuquerque, J., Anderson, J., & Zipf, A. (2023). A spatio-temporal analysis investigating completeness and inequalities of global urban building data in OpenStreetMap. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 3985.